

32nd VindKraftNet meeting :: Benchmarking/validation

17 November 2025

Eolus, Malmö, Sweden

Programme

10:00	Welcome and presentation of participants, sister org in ES Introduction to Eolus [00]	Lars Landberg, DNV
10:10	Turbulent Insights – Lessons from the 2025 BWE Ambient Turbulence Round Robin [01]	Martin Richter-Rose, Pavana
10:40	Validating other non-wake losses: Electrical Availability [02]	Andrew Henderson, COP
11:10	The Real Measurement Uncertainty of Floating LiDAR derived from Offshore Measurement Campaigns in the Republic of Korea [03]	Ishwar Mukesh, COP
11:40	Global 30 m Digital Terrain Model (DTM): Is It Time to Ditch Copernicus DEM for Wind & Renewables? [04]	Morten Lybech Thøgersen, EMD
12:10	Lunch	
13:10	The distribution vs correlation trade-off in MCP – what is it and how to address it [05]	Daniel H Svendsen, EMD
13:40	Untangling turbulence profiles with new lidar algorithms [06]	Frédéric Delbos, Vaisala
14:10	Validation of (Py)WAsP for wind resource assessment and numerical wind atlases. [07]	Rogier Ralph Floors, DTU
14:40	Break	
15:10	Next meeting (place and topic), Zenodo	Lars Landberg, DNV
16:00	End	

Next meeting: At: DTU/Risø; Topic: Climate Change; Spring 2026, Organiser: DNV
(lars.landberg@dnv.com)

/LL, 21/11/25

1 Our sister group in Spain "Vendaval"